

Fatih Sultan Mehmed Han Mosque in Heraklion

also known as “Hünkar Camii”, “Franciscan Monastery of Saint Francis”

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Entry tags: Christianity, Medieval Christians, Christian, Crete, Greece, Religious Group, Greek, Catholicism, Religious Place, Heraklion, Language, Turkic, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Catholic Christianity

The Sultan Mehmet Han Mosque was established after the Ottoman conquest of Heraklion in 1669 by converting the Franciscan monastery dedicated to Saint Francis, situated on a hill in the northeastern part of the city. The monastery was built upon the arrival of the Venetians on the island and served as an important focus for the spread of Franciscan ideology. It is mentioned as early as 1242. At the time of the conquest, the building consisted of twenty-three ground-floor and thirty upper-floor rooms in good condition, four reception rooms, four pavilions, four loggias, a kitchen, four cisterns, and four fountains. It also had three orchards, which had various trees such as arbors, cypresses, almond trees, caises, pomegranates, pears, and roses. Following the conquest, a medrese was established, and a minaret was constructed in place of the collapsed bell tower. According to Evliya Çelebi, the square bell tower of the temple had collapsed during the siege, and the minaret was rebuilt within forty days. Although visible from sea and land, the remote location meant it had a symbolic rather than practical role. The building complex was destroyed by an earthquake in 1856. The mosque continued to function until the early 20th century.

Date Range: 1242 CE - 1856 CE

Region: Fatih Sultan Mehmed Han Mosque in Heraklion

Region tags: Crete, Greece

The mosque was located on the site of the modern-day Archaeological Museum of Heraklion.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gerola, Giuseppe. *Monumenti Veneti Nell'isola Di Creta*. vol. 2. Venice: R. Instituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1918
- Source 2: Çelebi, Evliya. *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*. Topkapı Sarayı Kütüphanesi Bağdat 308 Numaralı Yazmanın Transkripsiyonu - Dizini. Edited by Seyit Ali Kahraman, Yücel Dağlı, and Robert Dankoff. Vol. 8. Istanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2003.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://koules.efah.gr>

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

– Source 1 URL: <https://explore.cure-project.gr>

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Years of excavation:

– Year range: N/A

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Ephorate of Antiquities of Heraklion

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: During the Ottoman period, the mosque was situated on a hill, distant from the city center.

Thus, it functioned more as a symbol of Ottoman domination of the city rather than a place that served the religious needs of the residents.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: During the Ottoman period, the mosque was situated on a hill, distant from the city center.

Thus, it functioned more as a symbol of Ottoman domination of the city rather than a place that served the religious needs of the residents.

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Mound

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general)

populace)

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Upon the demolition of the building in 1856, a chapel survived which continued to function as a mosque. Also, a door frame survived the earthquake, which had been donated to the monastery by Pope Alexander V. Recent excavations unearthed the underground level of the polygonal apse and the southern wing of the transept, which was utilized as a crypt for burials.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: Both as a monastery and as a mosque, the building served the purpose of both communal and individual worship.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: Parts of the structure were destroyed in 1856 by an earthquake. Later, the mosque was demolished in 1912, so that land could be found for the construction of the archaeological museum of Heraklion.

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Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: The mosque was demolished in 1912, so that land could be found for the construction of the archaeological museum of Heraklion.

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Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: It was destroyed by an earthquake in 1856.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The mosque was founded by the sultan who conquered Heraklion in 1669.

Specific to this answer:

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Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Notes: Heraklion was conquered after a 22-year siege and the establishment of the mosque commemorated the Ottoman conquest.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Expression of Ottoman dominance in the newly-conquered city

Notes: Upon the Ottoman conquest of a place, a process of spatial transformation took place, to project Ottoman power in the urban landscape. This takes place on a symbolic level through the construction of building complexes that indicate the Ottoman Empire's dominant position in the recently conquered city. This includes the conversion of temples into mosques.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Earth

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sand

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Clay

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Plaster

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Wood

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Stone

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: There might have been differences in theological perspectives and understandings within the empire.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Weekly

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are material offerings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

By all the community

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The male members of the Muslim community

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it required:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Priests

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Local elites

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Private contributions

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Wakf

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Imaret

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: There are two main festivals which take place annually, Ramazan Bayramı (Eid al-Fitr), marking the end of Ramadan and Kurban Bayramı (Eid al-Adha), the festival of sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Members of the Muslim community

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: There was a medrese (Islamic educational institution) that was a part of the complex

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Wakf

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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